

On the origin of the stability of foams made from catanionic surfactant mixtures

D. Varade,^a D. Carriere,^b L. R. Arriaga,^a
A.-L. Fameau,^{cd} E. Rio,^a D. Langevin^a and W. Drenckhan^{*a}

^a Laboratoire de Physique des Solides, Université of Paris Sud, Orsay, France.

E-mail: Wiebke.Drenckhan@u-psud.fr

^b UMR 3299 CEA/CNRS SIS2 M, LIONS (Laboratoire Interdisciplinaire sur l'Organisation Nanométrique et Supramoléculaire), France

^c UR1268 Biopolymères Interactions Assemblages Inra,
rue de la Géraudière, 44316 Nantes, France

^d Laboratoire Léon-Brillouin, CEA Saclay, 91191 Gif-sur-Yvette CEDEX, France

Received 3rd March 2011, Accepted 21st April 2011

DOI: 10.1039/c1sm05374d

Using mixtures of the anionic myristic acid ($C_{13}COOH$) and the cationic cetyl trimethylammonium chloride ($C_{16}TA^+Cl^-$) in aqueous solutions at a 2 : 1 ratio, we show that the outstanding stability of foams generated from sufficiently concentrated "catanionic" surfactant mixtures can be explained by a synergy effect between two fundamentally different mechanisms. Applying a multi-scale approach, in which we link static and dynamic properties of the bulk solutions, isolated gas/liquid interfaces, thin liquid films and foams, we identify these two mechanisms to be as follows: firstly, cationic mixtures create tightly packed surfactant layers at gas/liquid interfaces, which are strongly viscoelastic and also confer high disjoining pressures when two interfaces are approaching each other to form a thin liquid film. Foams created with such kind of interfaces tend to be extremely stable against coalescence (film rupture) and coarsening (gas exchange). However, typical time scales to cover the interfaces are much longer than typical foaming times. This is why a second mechanism plays a key role, which is due to the presence of micron-sized catanionic vesicles in the foaming solution. The bilayers of these vesicles are in a gel-like state, therefore leading to nearly indestructible objects which act like elastic micro-spheres. At sufficiently high concentrations, these vesicles jam in the presence of the confinement between bubbles, slowing down the drainage of liquid during the initial foaming process and therefore providing time for the interfaces to be covered. Furthermore, the tightly packed vesicles strongly reduce bubble coalescence and gas transfer between bubbles.

1 Introduction

Liquid foams consist of discrete gas bubbles dispersed in a continuous liquid phase. The presence of the bubbles, especially when closely packed, provides the liquid material with complex properties which are heavily exploited in industrial applications (food industry, cosmetics, precursors for solid foams, etc.) and provide a test bed to advance the fundamental understanding of the properties of complex, soft materials. ^{1,2} In both cases, it is necessary to render the foams sufficiently stable over the lifetime of an industrial product or an experiment. "Sufficiently stable" refers in this case to the slow-down or entire suppression of the three principal mechanisms at the heart of foam destruction: coalescence, coarsening and drainage. While coalescence refers to the rupture of the thin liquid film separating two neighbouring bubbles, coarsening is the result of gas transfer from smaller to bigger bubbles due to differences in the Laplace pressure, leading ultimately to the disappearance of the smaller bubbles. Both mechanisms, coalescence and coarsening, lead to a growth of the average bubble size with time. Drainage refers to the gravity driven flow of liquid along the liquid channels formed by intersecting foam films (the "Plateau borders"), leading to polyhedral bubble shapes and thin liquid films, which are more sensitive to coalescence and coarsening.

Foams are rendered stable against coalescence through the addition of interfacially active agents, which populate the gasliquid interfaces and provide steric (and often electrostatic) repulsion between interfaces and other stabilisation mechanisms, for example due to interfacial elasticities. ³ Coarsening can be slowed down and eventually suppressed by working with gases of low solubility and/or by using surface active substances which create solid-like bubble surfaces (such as proteins or particles ⁴). Drainage can be slowed down by increasing the bulk viscosity of the liquid, or by rendering it viscoelastic, for example through bulk gelification using polymers, liquid crystals, ⁵ particles ⁶⁻⁸ or emulsion droplets. ⁶⁻¹⁰

Unfortunately, the physico-chemical requirements for the suppression of each of the mechanisms can be very different and partially contradictory, leading to complex synergies when present in the same system. Furthermore, as a rule of thumb, systems which tend to make stable foams (for example protein or particle-stabilised foams) do not foam very well due to slow adsorption dynamics and/or the presence of adsorption barriers, i.e. good foam stability often infers bad foamability. It is therefore of great interest to find systems which have as few chemical ingredients as possible, but whose synergies allow to fight all three mechanisms of foam destabilisation simultaneously.

To achieve this goal we suggest here the application of catanionic surfactant systems, i.e. mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants. ^{11,12} Generally speaking, such mixtures are expected to show good properties with respect to foam formation and stabilisation for three principal reasons: (i) catanionic mixtures are known to pack very efficiently at the gas/water interface, ¹²⁻¹⁷ rendering the interfaces themselves strongly viscoelastic; ^{13,14,18-23} (ii) the critical micelle (or aggregation) concentration, although generally low in these

strongly non-ideal mixtures, has a finite value which provides free surfactant in solution ²⁴ and (iii) these mixtures form vesicles ²⁵ usually considered at thermodynamic equilibrium. ²⁶ The presence of vesicles provides bulk viscoelastic properties (ref. 27 and ref. 14-24 therein) and has been reported to provide good foam stabilities, ²⁸ but the underlying physical reason has not been clearly elucidated. More specifically, we have selected catanionic mixtures where the vesicles are in the so-called gel-phase, i.e. the bilayers are in the solid state. While preserving the three above-mentioned favourable properties, these solid-state bilayers additionally avoid too fast exchanges of the surfactant molecules between interfaces, vesicles and monomers, which potentially increase the life times of the foam once generated.

We prepared such catanionic systems from mixtures of the anionic myristic acid ($C_{13}COOH$) and the cationic cetyl trimethylammonium chloride ($C_{16}TA^+Cl^-$).²⁹ Depending on the composition, these mixtures consist of bilayers assembled into micron-sized aggregates of undefined geometry, or into stable (years) vesicles. With respect to the above-mentioned approach, relevant properties of these mixtures are: (i) air/solution equilibrium interfacial tension in the 20 – 30mNm⁻¹ range, ¹⁴ (ii) coexistence of the large assemblies with free cationic surfactant in the 10⁻⁴ to 10⁻² mol L⁻¹ range, and negligible concentration of myristic acid (< 10⁻⁶ mol L⁻¹)³⁰ and (iii) at an anionic/cationic ratio of 2/1, these mixtures form vesicles with solid bilayers at room temperature (melting point = 57°C). ³⁰ This is the ratio we have used throughout the work presented in this article. The vesicles contained in these mixtures may be strongly diluted without dissolution, or concentrated until they form closepacked arrangements that form macroscopic gels, without rupture or fusion over tens of months. ³¹ However, above a given hydrostatic or osmotic pressure threshold, the vesicles deform irreversibly following buckling patterns characteristic of their icosahedral symmetry and mechanical robustness. ^{32,33}

In our previous work, ¹⁴ we demonstrated that the foamability of these mixtures is essentially determined by the concentration of free surfactant, i.e. by the shortest surfactant adsorption time scale observed in the system. By contrast, the origin of the remarkable foam stability (initially reported as better than a few hours) is yet poorly understood. We therefore investigate here in more depth the origin of the stability of these catanionic foams, which we report to be even better than a few weeks. To illustrate the interplay of the various mechanisms at work in stabilising foams with the $C_{13}COOH/C_{16}TA^+Cl^-$ catanionic system, we introduce its general foaming properties at the outset of the article (Section 4) along with the hypothesis that the extraordinary stability of these foams ¹⁴ is provided by the interplay between highly viscoelastic gas/liquid interfaces and the presence of the vesicles. In order to prove this hypothesis, we consider in the remaining article the mechanisms at work at length scales of increasing complexity of the foam structure, starting with the properties of the gas/liquid interface (Section 5), continuing with the stability of individual films (Section 6) and the blocking of vesicles in films and Plateau border junctions (Section 7). We finish with a more quantitative analysis of the foamability and

foam stability (Section 8), bringing together the insights gained at the different length scales of the foam.

2 Materials, preparation and methods

2.1 Materials

Myristic acid ($C_{13}COOH$, Fluka; $M_w = 228 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) was recrystallized twice from hot acetonitrile, and cetyl trimethylammonium chloride (CTACl, $M_w = 320 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$, CMC = 0.36 g L^{-1}) was purchased from Sigma and used as such. Solutions were prepared with MilliQ water.

2.2 Solution preparation

The catanionic solution was prepared as reported in several publications.^{29,31,32} Suitable amounts of $C_{13}COOH$ and CTACl in a 2 ($C_{13}COOH$) : 1 (CTACl) ratio are mixed with water at a typical weight fraction of surfactant of 1% and heated at $50 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 days. The resulting mixture is dialyzed against a 100– fold volume of water (SpectraPor regenerated cellulose membranes, 10 kDa cutoff). In a typical experiment, the dialysis water is changed after 1 hour, 4 hours, 24 hours, 48 hours and 5 days of dialysis. It has been shown that in these conditions, the composition of the as-prepared vesicles is identical to that of the initial mixture ($C_{13}COOH : CTACl = 2 : 1, c = 1\%$), the vesicles encapsulate about 3 mM HCl , and that the pH of the outer solution remains identical to that of MilliQ water for several months (*ca.* pH = 6).^{29,31}

2.3 Foam production and characterisation

(1) Handshaking: foam samples were prepared by vigorous handshaking of cylindrical plastic containers (27 mm internal diameter, 120 mm height) filled with 20 – 25 mL of surfactant solution at a bulk concentration of $c = 0.5\text{wt}\%$.
(2) Turbulent mixing.³⁴ in the turbulent foaming device, the catanionic mixture and nitrogen meet at high pressure (5 bar) in a microscopic T-junction, generating polydisperse foams with a narrow bubble size-distribution with an average bubble size of around 300 micrometres.
(3) FoamScan: the FoamScan is a commercially available instrument (I.T. Concept), with which foamability (amount of foam generated during a certain time), foam stability (decay of foam volume as a function of time), and foam drainage (change of liquid volume in the foam as a function of time) can be measured. Foam is generated in a glass column (21 mm in diameter) by sparging nitrogen (N_2) through a fixed volume (12 mL) of the surfactant solution via a porous glass disc (pore size 14 – $60\mu\text{m}$ and thickness 3 mm). The gas flow rate was set and adjusted to 10, 35, 100, 150 mL min^{-1} to find out the optimum experimental conditions. The gas flow stopped automatically when the system had reached the preset foam volume (45 mL , which corresponds to 13 cm foam height). It has to be mentioned that the foam volume was always between 45 and 50

mL although the FoamScan was set to terminate foam generation once 45 mL are formed due to the mechanical limitations of the equipment (measuring foam volume and stopping the air flow is obviously no instantaneous process). The foam volumes as well as the subsequent foam decay are monitored by images of the column, which are constantly recorded by a CCD camera throughout the experiment. As a result one obtains the foam volume as a function of time. All measurements were performed at 25°C. Measurements were carried out a minimum of two times for reproducibility.

A pair of electrodes at the bottom of the column is used to measure the quantity of liquid that is not in the foam, while the volume of the liquid in the foam is measured by conductimetry using three pairs of electrodes located along the glass column. After calibration of the conductimetric electrodes, we can follow the liquid drainage of the foam via conductivity measurements at a fixed height of 6.5 cm above the base of the column.

2.4 Confocal microscopy

Confocal microscopy observations for bulk solution and foams have been performed with an Olympus IX 81 microscope equipped with a Fluoview FV1000 confocal head. The samples were labelled by electrostatic adsorption of the anionic Oregon green 488 isothiocyanate (Invitrogen) excited at 488 nm to the positively charged catanionic vesicles.^{29,31} The emitted fluorescence was collected through a 505 – 526 nm filter.

2.5 Thin Film Pressure Balance (TFPB)

Thin Film Pressure Balance (TFPB) is a homemade apparatus which allows to measure the disjoining pressure Π versus the thickness h of thin free-standing, horizontal foam films. Experimental details have been published elsewhere,³⁵ here we restrict ourselves to a very general description. The $\Pi - h$ curve is obtained by subjecting the film to a well-defined gas pressure and measuring its equilibrium thickness h interferometrically. The film is formed in a special, porous film holder, which is placed in a gastight measuring cell in such a way that the film is exposed to the gas pressure P_g , while a liquid reservoir, which is in contact with the film, is subjected to a reference pressure P_r . The pressure difference $\Delta P = P_g - P_r$ can be adjusted by a syringe system and is measured by a highly sensitive pressure difference transducer. Before measuring, the film holder was kept in the surfactant solution overnight in order to establish equilibrium. To make sure that the film holder did not pollute the solution, the surface tension of the solution was measured over a period of 2 h before each experiment to ensure that it remained unchanged ($\pm 0.1 \text{ mN m}^{-1}$). Eventually, the bottom of the cell was filled with excess solution to saturate the air and avoid evaporation. The lid of the cell was treated with a commercial antifogging agent. Measurements were conducted at least 5 h after closing the cell to ensure vapor-liquid equilibrium. All measurements were carried out at room temperature.

2.6 Tensiometry

We measured the surface tension γ using the Wilhelmy plate method and the rising bubble tensiometer apparatus³⁶ (Teclis, France). In the first method, the air-water interface is created in a homemade Teflon circular trough (8 cm diameter, 3 cm depth) and the surface tension is monitored by a pressure transducer (Nima, UK) until equilibrium is reached, whose value we denote γ_e . In the rising bubble method, the surface tension is calculated by image analysis from the shape of a bubble contained in the solution using the Laplace equation. The bubble is generated rapidly in order to start the measurement with an almost bare air/ solution interface, which allows to follow the surface tension changes ("dynamic surface tension" $\gamma(t)$) as surface active species arrive at the gas/liquid interface while keeping the bubble volume constant. Measurements are generally done until the equilibrium surface tension γ_e is reached, which can take a few hours, especially at low concentrations. The volume of the bubble was kept constant during the measurement and the solution is kept at room temperature. We evaluate surface tension data only when the Laplace equation can be safely applied, which is far before bubble detachment or the observation of non-Laplacian bubble shapes.

The dilational surface viscoelasticity was measured using the same setup³⁷ but in a mode which oscillates the bubble sinusoidally at an oscillation amplitude of 1% and a frequency of 0.1 Hz .

2.7 Bulk shear rheometer

The bulk shear properties of the catanionic solutions were studied using a standard shear rheometer (Anton Paar Physica MCR 300) using an embedded double Couette cylindrical system (DG 26.7, TEZ 150 P-C, Anton Paar). This geometry allows us to reduce the influence of boundary effects, considering equal shear rates inside and outside of the rotating cup due to its narrow gap ($\kappa = R_{\text{int}} / R_{\text{ext}} = 12.323/12.335 = 0.924$). We have performed strain-controlled experiments of the catanionic solutions using the oscillation mode, in which the inserted cup oscillates at a controlled angular frequency while the cell remains stationary. During the measurements, temperature is held constant at 25°C by a Peltier and the cell is covered by a cap in order to prevent evaporation and contamination.

2.8 Interfacial shear rheometer

The interfacial shear properties of the catanionic solutions were studied using a standard rotational rheometer (Anton Paar Physica MCR 301) with an embedded interfacial rheology system (IRS).³⁸ The IRS consists of a biconical disk (disk radius $R_2 = 34.14$ mm, cone angle $\alpha = 5^\circ$ and cone penetration depth $h_2 = 2.205$ mm) which is coupled to the top-driven motor and the torque transducer unit of the rheometer. The measuring cell consists of a cup made of glass (cup inner radius $R_1 = 40.00$ mm and cup height $h_1 = 45.00$ mm),

covered by an insulation jacket and fixed to the bottom part of the rheometer with a flange. The whole device is mounted on an antivibration table (Technical Manufacturing Corp., MA, USA). Once the solution is filled into the cup, the bicone is positioned at the interface using the normal force transducer. The solution level H_1 is determined as the bicone tip position for which the normal force changes the most by slowly approaching the bicone to the interface. Thus, the bicone midplane is positioned at the interface locating the bicone tip at $H_0 = H_1 - h_2$. We have performed strain-controlled experiments of the adsorbed catanionic films using the oscillation mode, in which the disk oscillates at a controlled angular frequency while the cup remains stationary. During the measurements, temperature is held constant at 25°C by a Peltier and the cell is covered by a cap in order to prevent evaporation and contamination.

Since the interfacial stresses are dissipated into the bulk phase, both interfacial and bulk flows will appear coupled, thus the experimentally measured torque exerted on the disk will be due not only to the interface but also to the bulk phase. Therefore, after data acquisition we have performed the numerical evaluation of the interfacial rheological parameters by using the commercial software developed by Anton Paar³⁸ on the basis of the interfacial and bulk velocity distributions obtained by Oh and Slattery.³⁹ This mathematical treatment allows to obtain the interfacial shear stress σ , storage G' and loss G'' moduli by solving the Stokes equations at low Reynolds numbers using the Boussinesq-Scriven interfacial stress tensor as boundary condition at the interface. Such interfacial analysis requires knowledge of the solution bulk viscoelasticity, which has been studied using the double Couette geometry as detailed in Section 2.7.

3 Bulk properties of the solutions

3.1 General properties

In this work we use mixtures of the anionic myristic acid ($C_{13}COOH$) and the cationic cetyl trimethylammonium chloride ($C_{16}TA^+Cl^-$) forming vesicles in equilibrium with free monomers of $C_{16}TA^+Cl^-$ at a concentration of $10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ ($[C_{13}COOH] < 10^{-6} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$).²⁹ They are prepared from a mixture of $C_{13}COOH$ and $C_{16}TA^+Cl^-$ at a molar ratio of 2 : 1 and a total initial surfactant concentration of 1wt%. The progressive dissolution of myristic acid crystals by cetyl trimethylammonium chloride above 50°C forms a white homogeneous and birefringent solution which contains elongated vesicles. During this cosolubilisation step, H^+Cl^- is released upon surfactant association. The subsequent dialysis step removes these inorganic ions outside the vesicles, whereas about 3mM H^+Cl^- remains encapsulated inside the vesicles.³¹ The resulting outwards osmotic pressure swells the vesicles.³² Samples prepared and dialysed at this ratio and concentration yield vesicles with a typical diameter of 5 – 10 μm , which are closely packed and therefore render the solution gel-like (left of Fig. 1). These vesicles show long-term stability (years): they tend to relax to their icosahedral shape as a result of H^+Cl^- leakage,³² but no fusion, dissolution,

etc. is observed. To obtain solutions at different surfactant concentrations, we dilute progressively the initial 1 wt % catanionic solution. This procedure does not destroy the vesicles but yields well-individualized vesicles (center and right of Fig. 1). We call attention to an important property of this system which is particularly relevant to the work presented here: the bilayers are in the gel phase i.e., they are solid-like bilayers with slow lateral diffusion and exchange with the outer solution.³⁰ As a consequence, the systems are quenched at the time scale of the experiment (weeks). Although it may result in slight creaming after several weeks, the dilution step does not induce noticeable changes in vesicle composition or diameter, but simply decreases the number density of the objects. The vesicles are stabilized by electrostatic charges. This charge is positive despite the 2 : 1 ratio in fatty acid/cationic surfactant (see ref. 29 and Fig. 1), as charge regulation effects strongly shift the dissociation equilibrium of the fatty acid towards reprotonation.^{40,41}

3.2 Rheological properties

As it is obvious from Section 3.1, the catanionic dispersions have a complex structure and therefore a complex bulk rheology. Quantifying the latter is of utmost importance in order to be able to determine correctly the interfacial properties of the mixtures (Sections 2.8 and 5.2) and to understand the foam stability (Section 8). We therefore dedicate here a special section to this topic.

We have performed strain-controlled experiments of the catanionic solution at $c = 0.5\text{wt}\%$ at a constant temperature ($T = 25^\circ\text{C}$). Fig. 2a shows the stress (σ) versus strain (ε) curves of the system at two different angular frequencies, $\omega = 1$ and 10rads^{-1} . At low frequencies ($\omega = 1\text{rads}^{-1}$) the catanionic vesicle suspension exhibits a non-linear viscoelastic behaviour above a yield stress of $\sigma_y = 0.5 \times 10^{-3}$ Pa. In contrast, at high enough frequencies ($\omega = 10\text{rads}^{-1}$) it behaves nearly linear (the yield stress is no longer measurable) but fluid-like ($G' < G''$), as evidenced by inspection of the storage and loss moduli (respectively $G' \leq 0.01$ Pa, i.e. the shear elastic modulus is below the experimental resolution limit, and $G'' \approx \eta\omega$ with $\eta = 0.007\text{Pas}$) (Fig. 2b). The fact that the shear elastic modulus decreases with frequency above an angular frequency of $ca.3\text{rads}^{-1}$ reveals a dynamic softening and indicates that the yield stress has been reached at this frequency causing afterwards a decrease in the elastic modulus. A very important point relevant to the discussion about foam stability (Section 8) is that at low concentrations (below $0.1\text{wt}\%$) the solutions do not display a measurable elastic behaviour ($G' \approx 0$) and therefore no yield stress. Fig. 2b shows simultaneously the different parameters measured maintaining the strain at a constant value inside the linear regime ($\varepsilon = 1\%$) while varying the angular frequency ω from 0.1 to 10rads^{-1} . We can see that the viscoelasticity of the system is characterised by a continuous increase of G' and G'' as a function of ω , the system being more elastic than viscous (i.e. $G' > G''$) for the range of frequencies between 0.1 and 1 rad s^{-1} . The rather large values of the low-frequency viscosity indicate that the volume fraction of vesicles is large enough to disturb the neighbourhood of other vesicles resulting in an increased

viscosity with respect to pure water ($\eta = 0.001 \text{ Pa s}$). We find values of the zero shear viscosity as high as $\eta_0 = 0.09 \text{ Pa s}$ and a noticeable shear thinning, i.e. a significant decrease in the measured viscosity with increasing shear rate, as shown in Fig. 2c. Fluid flow between adjacent vesicles is expected to contribute to the suspension viscosity as $\eta = \eta_S R/d$,⁴² η_S being the solvent viscosity (here water), R the vesicle size and d the separation of the vesicles. R/d can therefore be taken as a geometrical enhancement factor accounting for the shear gradients present in the fluid which separates a vesicle from its neighbours. From confocal microscopy (central image of Fig. 1) one can approximate that $R/d \approx 10$, which yields inter-vesicle contributions of the order of 0.01 Pa s , i.e. an order of magnitude below the measured viscosity. Thus, we postulate vesicle shape deformations as the dominant dissipating mechanism when $R/d > 1$, i.e. when the distance d between vesicles is smaller than their radius R . It is difficult to estimate such contribution but it must be of higher order, i.e. $\eta = \eta_S (R/d)^x$ with $x \geq 2$. The significant shear thinning (Fig. 2c) observed in vesicle suspensions of high enough concentration ($c = 0.5\text{wt}\%$) as compared to the diluted ones (see $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$ in Fig. 2c, for which $R/d < 1$, as seen in right image of Fig. 1) is in good agreement with the theoretical model proposed by Denkov et al.⁴³ and the experimental observations of Princen.⁴⁴ We find that the best power fit for the observed shear thinning in our system is $\eta = 3.16 \times 10^{-3} \varepsilon^{-(0.49 \pm 0.01)}$, pointing out viscous friction as the mechanism responsible for such behavior as in the case of foams or concentrated emulsions.^{43,44} The fact that the viscosity of very diluted vesicle suspensions, i.e. in the concentration range between 0.001 and 0.1wt%, is no longer shear rate dependent is relevant when analysing interfacial shear rheology data, as done in Section 5.2.

To sum up the key features of the bulk properties of the catanionic mixtures: due to the presence of solid-like vesicles they display a complex flow behaviour. Their viscosity depends on the vesicle concentration, and beyond a critical concentration ($c > 0.1\text{wt}\%$) the solutions become notably non-Newtonian with the presence of a well-defined yield stress and a significant shear thinning behaviour. The interplay of these properties plays an important role in the foamability and foam stability of these mixtures, which is discussed in detail in Section 8.

4 Qualitative foaming properties

Fig. 3 shows a typical image sequence of a foam generated from a 0.5wt% catanionic mixture by handshaking (Section 2.3). The mixture shows only moderate foamability (left of Fig. 3) but outstanding foam stability (life time of some weeks) in comparison to standard surfactant foams. The foam stability here is characterised by three key features:

- (1) Complete absence of bubble coalescence,
- (2) Very slow gravity-driven drainage of liquid out of the foam and
- (3) Very slow coarsening.

The slow drainage is illustrated in Fig. 4, which shows the time evolution

of a foam generated from the same mixture using turbulent mixing (Section 2.3). Whilst a standard surfactant foam with the same bubble size and liquid fraction drains in about one hour, the catanionic foam drains in about one day. It is furthermore noticeable that even when drainage stops, the foam remains visibly "wet", i.e. a significant amount of liquid remains trapped between the bubbles. It usually takes these catanionic foams a few months to disappear completely-via coarsening and the slow release of liquid as bubbles grow. We would also like to point out the separation of the foam into a bottom part with small bubbles and a top part with significantly larger bubbles (after 1 week in Fig. 4), whose origin is discussed in more detail in Section 8.

We propose here that these unusual foam properties are due to a synergetic effect between the presence of very stable microscopic vesicles and strongly viscoelastic gas/liquid interfaces formed by this catanionic mixture. A first indication of this fact is given by looking at the foaming behaviour of a sonicated catanionic mixture, in which the vesicles have been destroyed such that only microscopic pieces of bilayers remain (left of Fig. 5). This solution is stable over the time scale of our experiments, i.e. the vesicles do not reform. Fig. 5 shows images of the nonsonicated (top) and sonicated (bottom) solution and their corresponding foams. It is clear that the foamability decreases dramatically upon destruction of the vesicles, whilst the foam stability remains similar. In the following we attempt to elucidate this peculiar behaviour by considering the properties of the catanionic mixtures at various length scales of the foam.

5 Interfacial properties

5.1 Surface tension

The equilibrium surface tension of all the catanionic solutions in the concentration range used in this article is independent of the surfactant concentration and around 28mNm^{-1} . This is very low in comparison to pure CTA^+ solutions, whose surface tension remains above $\gamma_e \approx 34\text{mNm}^{-1}$ even when the CMC is reached at about $c = 0.01 \text{ g L}^{-1}$. It is well-known that catanionic mixtures can have a very low surface tension at very low surfactant concentration,¹² which is a result of synergetic effects between the oppositely charged surfactants, leading to an enhanced surface coverage. This was confirmed recently by Stocco et al. for the catanionic mixture used here.¹⁴ The high surface coverage also leads to unique rheological properties of the interfaces, which are discussed in more detail in Section 5.2.

Whilst the equilibrium surface tension is independent of the cationic concentrations in the range employed in this report, the time taken by the system to reach this equilibrium varies over almost an order of magnitude. This is reflected in the dynamic surface tension measurements $\gamma(t)$, which are shown in the top graph of Fig. 6 for different catanionic concentrations ($c = 0.001, 0.01$ and $0.1\text{wt}\%$). In contrast to simple surfactant solutions, the surface tension decays here in two well-defined relaxations, the first one dropping the surface tension

to a value of around 60 mN m^{-1} and the second one more dramatically to the equilibrium value around 25 mN m^{-1} . The latter is in good agreement with the equilibrium surface tensions measured by the Wilhelmy plate method (Section 2.6).

Stocco et al.¹⁴ investigated the nature of these two relaxation times for different molecular ratios of the same catanionic mixtures. They demonstrated that the first relaxation is controlled by the presence of a small concentration of free CTA⁺ in the solution. Consistently, the surface tension reached after this first relaxation decreases as the concentration of free CTA⁺ increases. They suggest that the second relaxation may either be due to the presence of an electrostatic adsorption barrier or to the slow release of surfactants from the solid-like aggregates. More insight on the role of the aggregates may be gained by comparing the dynamic surface tension of sonicated and non-sonicated mixtures (compare left column of Fig. 5), as shown in Fig. 7 for two surfactant concentrations ($c = 0.01$ and $c = 0.1 \text{ wt}\%$). Whilst the first surface tension drop remains almost unchanged, the second one occurs much earlier in the sonicated samples. Such an observation gives way to a number of different interpretations. One which seems plausible considers that upon sonication vesicles are destroyed into smaller bilayer pieces, which diffuse faster and hence reach the proximity of the interface more rapidly. Since the typical diffusion time is proportional to the particle size, a size reduction by an order of magnitude would lead to a reduction of the diffusion time by an order of magnitude, which is roughly what we observe. Consistently, the diffusion time also decreases as the object density in the bulk is increased. However, it scales with the concentration as $c^{1/2}$, rather than with c^2 , as would be expected in a purely diffusion-limited process. This is why the diffusion of objects was discarded by Stocco et al. The release of surfactants from the solid-like aggregates might be facilitated if they are bilayer pieces, but at this stage it is difficult to exclude completely the role of the electrostatic barriers.

Even if for the moment the dynamic surface tension curves are only qualitatively explained, the measurements provide nevertheless an important indication of the potential foaming behaviour of the mixtures. During foam generation bubbles need to be rapidly covered with surfactant to avoid coalescence when they come into contact. Rapidly adsorbing surfactants are therefore an essential ingredient for successful foam generation. This is certainly not the case for the catanionic mixture used here, where the essential surface tension drop occurs after more than 100 s even for the more concentrated solutions. Most foaming processes involve the mixing of gas and liquid at reasonably high speed and the surfactants are transported to the air/liquid surface by convection rather than by diffusion (as in the dynamic surface tension experiments). The time scales provided by the surface tension curves should therefore only serve as an indication. Many of our measurements confirm, however, that even in dynamic conditions they remain much longer than typical time scales required for good foaming (see Section 9). We therefore assign the main reason why the mixtures are nevertheless reasonably good foamers to the presence of the vesicles, which is discussed in more detail in Sections 7 and 8.

5.2 Interfacial rheology

Foams are continuously evolving systems in which liquid drains and the average bubble size increases due to bubble coalescence or coarsening. As a result, the dynamic properties of the surfactant-covered gas/liquid interfaces⁴⁵ play an important role in foam stabilisation.⁴⁶ The bottom of Fig. 6 shows how the dilational elastic modulus⁴⁷ of the gas/liquid interface (measured at a frequency of 0.1 Hz using the oscillating bubble method (Section 2.6)) changes with time for two different cationic concentrations. It is observed that the second relaxation in the dynamic surface tension coincides well with the build-up of a highly elastic interfacial layer. After diffusion of the large objects (vesicles or bilayers after sonication) to the interface, the surfactants therefore rearrange to form a mixed interfacial layer. At this point, the interface is almost solid-like and the bubble shapes become rapidly non-Laplacian. As a result, the values of $E > 500\text{mNm}^{-1}$ provided in Fig. 6 should only be considered as an indication, but compare relatively well to the bidimensional Young's (stretching) modulus measured in the vesicles made of the same cationic system (500mNm^{-1} (ref. 32)) and outline in any case the highly elastic character of the interface after adsorption is complete.

In order to characterise better such strongly viscoelastic interfaces, we determined their shear rheological properties using an interfacial shear rheometer (Section 2.8). After data acquisition we performed the numerical evaluation of the shear parameters taking into account the bulk rheology data (Section 3.2), as is described in Section 2.8. Fig. 8 shows the variation of (a) the interfacial stress σ_i and (b) the interfacial storage and loss moduli, G_i' and G_i'' , respectively, as a function of the strain ε applied to the interface. The experiments were made at a constant angular frequency $\omega = 6.2\text{rads}^{-1}$ and a bulk concentration of 0.1wt%. At this frequency the bulk cationic mixture is fluid ($G'' \approx 0.043\text{ Pa}$; $G' \approx 0$, from Fig. 2c). However, the adsorbed layer at the air/water interface exhibits strongly viscoelastic behavior. Fig. 8a clearly points out that the linear viscoelastic regime of such layers is limited to very small strains ($\varepsilon < 0.3\%$). Fig. 8 b shows that the interfacial storage modulus G_i' remains constant below the critical yield stress but above it exhibits a power-law decay $G_i' \propto \varepsilon' = \varepsilon^{-(1.45 \pm 0.02)}$. In contrast, the interfacial loss modulus G_i'' presents a maximum before falling as $G_i'' \propto \varepsilon'' = \varepsilon^{-(0.68 \pm 0.01)}$. We therefore find that the power of the strain dependence is nearly double for G_i' than for G_i'' ($\nu'/\nu'' \approx 2$). Both features, the pronounced peak in the interfacial loss modulus and the relation $\nu'/\nu'' \approx 2$, are robust features of the typical behaviour of soft glassy materials,⁴⁸ which has been observed for a large variety of complex bulk fluids, such as concentrated suspensions, emulsions, foams or polymers.⁴⁸ However, to our knowledge there exist very few studies which show the same kind of behaviour for quasi-two-dimensional systems, i.e. for interfaces.^{49–51} The observed similarities suggest a possibly common underlying mechanism with soft glassy bulk systems, i.e. a decrease in the structural relaxation time driven by the increasing strain.^{48,52}

To obtain further insights into the underlying mechanism we studied the

evolution of G_i' and G_i'' as a function of the angular frequency (Fig. 9). We used different concentrations, starting the experiments after 30 minutes equilibration time, and using a fixed value of the strain ($\varepsilon = 0.05\%$) well inside the linear viscoelastic regime (see Fig. 8). We find a very similar behaviour for all concentrations: the interfacial storage modulus continuously increases with angular frequency until it reaches a plateau, in contrast to the interfacial loss modulus which decreases, exhibiting a shallow minimum at the higher angular frequencies experimentally accessible. In addition, at the lowest frequencies, there appears a crossover from a liquid-like ($G_i' < G_i''$) to a solidlike ($G_i' > G_i''$) behaviour, which points out again the presence of a structural relaxation. This crossover is shifted to higher frequencies when the catanionic suspension is diluted (see the inset in Fig. 9). Since the process is induced by shear, the structural relaxation must occur in the plane of the interface where the torque is applied and since the layer is not compressed, adsorption/desorption processes play no role. At this stage it is not clear to us, what exactly the nature of the interfacial structure could be and which kind of phenomena lead to the concentration-dependent structural relaxation. Further investigations of this question are planned in the near future.

However, despite the uncertainty of the precise nature of the interfacial composition/structure, we confirmed that the gas/ liquid interfaces are highly viscoelastic and therefore contribute to an efficient foam stabilisation.

6 Film properties

Since the stability of foams is controlled by the stability of the thin films which separate bubbles, we investigated the properties of isolated, horizontal films of catanionic mixtures in the Thin Film Pressure Balance (Section 2.5).

In order to study the influence of the equilibration times, we initially created a very thick film in the film holder which was then put into the cell. In order to form a thin film we applied a large pressure drop either immediately, after 5 hours or after 24 hours. Independently of the equilibration time we find that all films were formed only at very high pressure (> 2000 Pa), which re-confirms the presence of a finite bulk yield stress (Section 3.2). Additionally, the films form very slowly (order of minutes instead of seconds as in the case of standard surfactants).

The films rupture immediately when the pressure is applied without an equilibration time, while the stability increases significantly with equilibrium time. Our observations correlate well with the slow dynamics witnessed by the surface tension measurements: the film stability is greatly enhanced once the gas/ liquid interface is sufficiently covered by the surface active mixture. The film stability also depends significantly on the catanionic concentration. While films created from solutions of $c = 0.01\text{wt}\%$ (after 5 hour equilibration time, i.e. long after full surface coverage is reached) lasted for a few minutes at 2000 Pa, those of $c = 0.05\text{wt}\%$ were stable for at least 3-4 hours. As full surface coverage is achieved in both cases, this outlines the contribution of the bulk properties of the

solution (which vary with concentration) in addition to the surface properties.

This is confirmed by direct inspection of the films. Fig. 10 shows representative examples of the time evolution, i.e. the progressive thinning of such films for three different cationic concentrations ($c = 0.01\text{wt}\%$, $0.05\text{wt}\%$ and $0.1\text{wt}\%$ after 24 hours of equilibration) once a pressure of 2000 Pa is applied. As can be seen by the variation of interference colours, the film thickness is highly heterogeneous. The fact that the typical object size is of the order of $10\mu\text{m}$ leads us to believe that vesicles remain trapped in the film, possibly with strong deformation,³² but without destruction. This is rather unusual, since objects of this size are normally expelled from thin liquid films due to the presence of strong capillary forces. However, as shown in Section 5.2, the gas/liquid interface becomes very rigid after sufficiently long equilibration times, which may well enable the trapping of objects. Similar observations have been made with films containing protein aggregates.⁵³

Films created from $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$ (bottom of Fig. 10) were extremely stable and could be observed for more than 8 h. These films were also resistant to applied pressure ramps or pressure steps, exhibiting the same appearance before and after the cycle. This indicates that there is no rearrangement of the structures at the film surface and we may conclude that, at sufficiently high concentrations, the vesicles form gel-like networks in the film.

In all cases, even when only a few vesicles are present such that parts of the film are homogenous (see the top sequence of Fig. 10), the equilibrium film thickness remains unusually thick, i.e. above 200 nm. This is at least an order of magnitude thicker than for films made of standard ionic surfactant solutions (a few tens of nm). This indicates the presence of a strong disjoining pressure³⁵ between the two gas/liquid interfaces, assigned to the high (positive) surface charge density. It has been shown that the electrostatic force in lamellar phases made of cetyl trimethylammonium myristate is a delicate balance between surface charge density (favoured here by the release of HCl from the destroyed vesicles) and electrostatic screening (also favoured by the presence of HCl).^{40,41} In the most favourable cases, it has been predicted and observed that these electrostatic repulsions are sufficient to swell such lamellar phases up to 60 nm at comparable applied pressures, which scales consistently with the distances observed here, but still underestimates the measured values.

Measurements in the Thin Film Pressure Balance may seem somewhat artificial in comparison to the conditions encountered in real foams. However, qualitatively we make the same kind of observations (thick films and film-corrugation) in films contained in a cationic foam. A particularly striking example is given in Fig. 11, which shows a centimetre-sized film which was stable for a few days. To sum up, we find that the film stability is greatly enhanced when the films are left to equilibrate until full surface coverage by the cationic mixture is achieved, as indicated by the dynamic surface tension measurements in Section 5.1. Furthermore, the films remain very thick and the formation of network-like structures by vesicles within the film at sufficiently high cationic concentrations provides additional resistance to rupture, rendering the films indestructible on the time scales and pressure conditions accessible in our experiments.

It is important to note here that care needs to be taken with cationic concentrations when relating these observations to the properties of foams, as we do in Sections 8 and 10. The films are held in a porous frit, which probably filters large vesicles or vesicle-aggregates. The concentrations indicated in the film experiments could therefore be underestimated.

7 Local foam properties

Before thin films are formed between bubbles, as analysed in Section 6, the foam needs to drain. We investigated in detail how the liquid drains out between bubbles under gravity for cationic solutions at different concentrations using confocal microscopy (Section 2.4). Two typical (but extreme) examples are shown in Fig. 12 for the case of $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$ and $c = 1\text{wt}\%$.

In the case of $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$ (Fig. 12a) one can clearly identify the interfaces of the bubbles, which implies that they are attractive for the fluorescent probe (Oregon Green 488) and must therefore be positively charged, similarly to the initial bilayers (Section 3.1). As liquid drains out between the bubbles (images from left to right) one observes an increased trapping and compaction of vesicles and vesicle aggregates between the bubbles, even within the thin films separating bubbles (inset of top right image), confirming once more the trapping of vesicles in the films (as discussed in Section 6). For sufficiently high concentrations (Fig. 12b) we observe an immediate and complete blocking of Plateau borders by vesicles and hence a dramatic slow-down, and finally full arrest of drainage. How these local observations act on the entire scale of the foam is discussed in the following.

8 Quantitative foaming

In order to understand how the various system parameters intervene more quantitatively in the cationic foams, we performed measurements using the Foam-Scan device (Section 2.3). Fig. 13a shows two examples of how the foam height increases with time as gas is injected at a constant flow rate (35 mL min^{-1}) into the solution via a porous frit until the foam reaches a volume of 45 mL, corresponding to a foam height of 13 cm. Experiments were made with different concentrations of cationic mixtures ($c = 0.05$ and $0.5\text{wt}\%$). Bubble diameters in the generated foam are of the order of 1 mm. The foam height increases linearly with time and the rate of foam generation corresponds to the rate of gas injection, with some small correction due to the amount of liquid entrained in the foam in this process. From this general observation we can already conclude that negligible bubble coalescence takes place in both samples during foam generation. No noticeable difference is observed between the two concentrations. This is very different, once foam generation is stopped. Fig. 13b displays the foam height variation with foam age, i.e. the time elapsed after stopping the gas injection. While the foam made with the more concentrated

mixture is reasonably stable, with a decrease of foam height of about 25% in 6000 s (= 100 min), the less concentrated one collapses dramatically within the first 800 s (~ 10 min). Both concentrations have the same equilibrium surface tension and should therefore create equally stable foams once the interfaces are populated. However, what distinguishes the two mixtures is the time to reach equilibrium and the amount of vesicles present in the solutions, which increase the solution viscosity and lead to a finite yield stress for the more concentrated mixture (Section 3.2). As can be seen at the top of Fig. 6, a gas/liquid interface of a catanionic mixture of 0.05wt% takes about 1000 s to equilibrate (at rest), which means that the foam drains and collapses before the interfaces are populated. The energy input during foam generation could reduce this time somewhat, helping to bring surfactants to the interface more quickly than in the case of an interface at rest, but a number of our observations seem to indicate that the orders of magnitude of the time scales remain similar. This fact is discussed in more detail in Section 9.

In the case of $c = 0.5\text{wt}\%$ interfacial equilibration times are of the order of a few hundred seconds, i.e. still much longer than the typical time scale of foam generation, but here the vesicle concentration is high enough to slow down the drainage of liquid, and to avoid that bubbles come into close contact during the equilibration time (and possibly after), as discussed in Section 7, hence providing a significant increase in foam stability. Fig. 13c illustrates foam ageing for different concentrations. Very similar observations have been made by Novales and coworkers for the case of vesicle containing fatty-acid-lysine dispersions.²⁸

From these general observations it is obvious that there should be a critical catanionic concentration beyond which interfacial equilibration and the blocking by the vesicles interplay in such a way as to render the foams very stable. Such kind of interplay depends strongly on the bubble size of the foam, as has been shown very recently for the case of foams doped with particles.^{6,7} To demonstrate this for the case of our vesicles, we varied the flow rate ($10 - 150 \text{ mL min}^{-1}$) at which the gas is injected into the mixture, which produces bubble sizes which vary over a factor of five ($0.7 - 3.5 \text{ mm}$), as shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 15 shows how the foaming process and the foam stability depend on the gas flow rate (i.e. on the bubble size) for a catanionic mixture of $c = 0.5\text{wt}\%$ (Fig. 15 c and d) and-for comparison-for a CTABr solution (Fig. 15a and b). For both systems and at all flow rates, negligible bubble coalescence occurs during foam generation, as indicated by the linear increase in foam height. However, the two systems differ significantly in terms of foam stability. Whilst the gas flow rate has a negligible influence on the stability of the CTABr-foams, it influences strongly the stability of the catanionic foams. More specifically, foam stability increases dramatically with decreasing flow rate, i.e. with decreasing bubble size. In particular, foams generated at 10 mL min^{-1} (bubble sizes of the order of 0.7 mm , Fig. 14) are superstable, with no sign of coalescence over a few days. The initial dip in the foam height is a result of liquid draining out of the foam, hence reducing its total height without destroying bubbles. The fact that

the foam stability increases with decreasing flow rate is an indication that the foam stability is not enhanced by an additional energy input, which generally helps to accelerate slow adsorption dynamics of surfactants to the interface,⁵⁴ but that another concentration- and/or bubble size-dependent mechanism (see Fig. 13 and 14) is at work here. The same "superstability" is observed for foams generated by turbulent mixing (Section 2.3) which is shown in Fig. 4. Bubble sizes are of the order of a few hundred micrometres. Hence, it seems that below a critical bubble size the blocking of the vesicles becomes very efficient.

This fact is emphasised in Fig. 16, which shows the evolution of the liquid fraction φ , i.e. the relative amount of liquid in the foam, measured at a height of 6.5 cm for the same systems as presented in Fig. 15. The behaviour of the CTABr system (Fig. 16a and b) is that of a classic soap foam: with increasing gas flow rate, more liquid is entrained during foam generation, hence the liquid fraction of the final foam increases significantly with gas flow rate (Fig. 16a). The increase of liquid fraction with time during foam generation has a complex shape, since first the foam needs to arrive at the electrodes and furthermore the foam drains during the generation process. Once the foam generation is stopped, the drainage of liquid in foams generated at different flow rates (and therefore having different bubble sizes) is very similar (Fig. 16a), as expected in this bubble size range.^{2,55}

The behaviour of the catanionic mixtures (Fig. 16c and d) is very different: the final liquid fraction after foam generation is very similar for all flow rates and is maximum for the lowest flow rate, indicating that more bulk solution is entrained during the foam generation. The fact that the liquid fraction at low flow rates is even higher than that of the CTABr is due to the increased viscosity of the bulk solution due to the presence of the vesicles. The presence of a finite yield stress (Section 3.2) should not play a role, as it is easily overcome by the typical shear stresses encountered during bubble generation. The fact that faster foam generation entrains less liquid is likely due to the shear thinning effects in the typical shear rate range encountered during foam formation, pointed out in Section 3.2. A higher foam formation rate implies higher shear stresses and shear rates and therefore a more fluid-like behaviour and lower viscosities. A significant difference is also observed for the drainage behaviour of the foams once the foam generation is stopped. The liquid drainage is slowed down with decreasing bubble size and remains at different finite values at long times. Typical shear rates encountered during foam drainage in our foams should not contribute greatly to shear thinning effects. On the contrary, the fact that smaller bubbles (which have smaller Plateau borders at the same liquid fraction, hence higher shear rates) drain slower than larger ones is an indication that shear thinning cannot be the controlling factor. We therefore believe that the slow-down and final stop of drainage is mostly controlled by the presence of a finite yield-stress which appears once drainage sufficiently concentrates the vesicles (above 0.1wt%, see Section 3.2).

The typical shear stress τ encountered in the Plateau borders of radius r in a foam at rest under gravity g may be written as:

$$\tau \approx r\rho g \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density of the liquid. The typical Plateau border radius r in a foam with an average bubble diameter D_B at a liquid fraction φ may be approximated as.⁵⁶

$$r \approx D_B \varphi^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Putting eqn (1) and (2) together provides us with an approximation of the typical bubble size D_B^* needed to block the vesicles, i.e. to be below the yield stress of the solutions (refer to Section 3.2)

$$D_B^* \approx \left(\rho g \varphi^{1/2} \right)^{-1} \tau_y \quad (3)$$

Considering that we have typical liquid fractions of $\varphi \approx 0.15\%$ (Fig. 16) and a yield stress of $\tau \approx 0.5 \times 10^{-3}$ Pa, one finds that vesicles should be blocked for bubbles sizes of a few hundred microns. This is indeed the case for foams produced by turbulent mixing (Fig. 4) and at 10 mL min^{-1} in the FoamScan device. The drainage which follows this blocking may be mostly the drainage of liquid between the vesicles resulting in the densely packed vesicle structures in the Plateau borders which we observe under the microscope. Similar trends have been observed for mixtures of surfactants and high concentrations of hydrophilic particles^{6–8} or emulsion droplets,^{9,10,57} relating in particular the dependence of the blocking of drainage as a function of the ratio between particle and bubble size.⁶ However, we refrain here from making more quantitative comparisons due to the complexity of the subject and lack of truly systematic investigations for our catanionic mixtures for this purpose. This carefulness also results from the fact that we are not sure how reliably the conductivity reflects the liquid fraction when the Plateau borders are blocked with vesicles whose encapsulated ions pass only with great difficulty.³¹ Hence, the measured liquid fraction may be significantly smaller than the actual one once the vesicle concentration becomes high. Our observations seem to confirm this, but more quantitative investigations need to be performed.

9 Further discussions

In trying to relate not only different length scales but also typical time scales of the foaming and foam stability process, we encounter a very common problem: we need to compare experiments conducted in static conditions, such as the surface tension or film experiments, with those conducted in dynamic conditions, such as the foaming experiments. Since our key argument is related to the fact that the presence of vesicles is needed to avoid the formation of thin films before the interfaces are sufficiently populated with surfactants, we would like to provide some additional arguments here.

Much of our arguments are based on the time scales measured for the second surface tension drop in Fig. 6. Even if this experiment relies entirely on diffusion for surfactant transport, we have conducted a number of experiments, which show us that the time to reach full surface coverage remains similar, even in different experimental conditions. First of all, we oscillated the bubble during the surface tension measurement and found that the surface tension drop occurred after the same time. This shows that an additional energy input at the interface does not accelerate the adsorption process. The same observation holds for the measurements of the surface elasticity E (Fig. 6b), which are conducted in dynamic conditions. Furthermore, we tried many different techniques to generate individual bubbles and films in dynamic conditions and found that whenever thin films were formed before the typical equilibration times given in Fig. 6, the films ruptured immediately, making it therefore impossible to perform well-controlled experiments on fresh films without the presence of vesicles. In cases where we could generate a thick film, even without the presence of the vesicles, and allow the interfaces to equilibrate - as we did for the measurements in the Thin Film Balance-the stability of the films was greatly enhanced. Hence, even if not verified quantitatively, after the many kind of observations we have performed with this system, we believe that the slow adsorption dynamics are present in the system even under the kind of dynamic conditions encountered in our experiments and that the key difference to ensure foam stability at shorter times is provided by the vesicles.

Another important point to discuss here concerns the coarsening behaviour of the cationic foams. Up to now we have discussed the foam stability mostly in terms of drainage and bubble coalescence. This is due to the fact that coarsening is extremely slow in these systems¹⁴ and therefore not relevant on the typical time scales of our experiments. But many important questions are related to this slow coarsening. For the moment it is not clear whether the slow coarsening is due to

- the very closely packed interfacial layer, which acts as a gas barrier,
- the high elasticity of the interfacial layer, which counteracts coarsening,⁵⁸ or
- the presence of closely packed vesicles between the bubbles, which slow down significantly the gas transfer by thickening significantly the films and by rendering a significant part of the film non-transparent for the gas.

Fig. 4 may provide some important indication for this. One can see that at long time scales, the average bubble size at the top of the foam increases more rapidly than in the remaining foam (without bubble coalescence). The coarsening remains much slower than that of standard surfactant foams. Closer analysis by microscopy shows that the top part of the foam is essentially free of vesicles, which must have drained. This fact allows two conclusions. Firstly, after sufficiently long times, the foams remain extremely stable against bubble coalescence even without the presence of vesicles, which is in agreement with

the observations on individual films (Section 6). Secondly, even without vesicles, the coarsening is slowed down significantly, yet measurably faster than in the presence of the vesicles, indicating an important role of the interfaces.

10 Conclusions/outlook

We have shown in this article how synergies between oppositely charged amphiphiles can lead to simultaneous synergies on different length and time scales of a foam and therefore contribute significantly to its stability. The electrostatic interactions between the amphiphiles lead to the formation of highly close-packed monolayers at the gas/liquid interfaces and therefore to unusually low interfacial tensions and high interfacial viscoelasticities. This contributes significantly to the stabilisation of foams, but suffers from slow dynamics and is therefore inefficient during foam generation. Simultaneously, the same electrostatic interactions lead to the formation of micron-sized aggregates with rigid bilayers in the bulk. These increase the viscosity of the liquid and lead to the presence of a finite yield stress. Whilst the increased viscosity slows down the drainage of liquid in the films and the Plateau borders of the foam, the finite yield stress may entirely stop it. Both phenomena therefore contribute significantly to the stability of the foam during its generation and at longer times. In particular, we could demonstrate that a correlation exists between the bubble and the vesicle size and concentration. Furthermore, both the densely packed surfactant layers at the gas/liquid interfaces and the presence of the vesicles dramatically slow down the coarsening process in such foams.

Understanding such kind of synergies on different length scales plays an important role in a general movement towards the development and application of multi-hierarchical materials in the realm of soft chemistry.⁵⁹ Foams play an important role in this,⁴⁶ offering already two natural levels of structuration on the bubble scale (microns to millimetres) and on the film scale (nanoto micrometres). An additional structuration via the addition of polymers, emulsion drops,^{9,57} aggregates or particles^{4,6,7} can dramatically change the properties and is therefore intensely investigated-especially as templates for porous materials.⁵⁹⁻⁶²

The interplay between the various parameters controlling foam stability is very complex and naturally, many questions remain to be explored for this and similar system.⁶³ We consider of particular importance the curious interfacial properties and the interaction between the interfaces and the vesicles.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Thomas Zemb for having initiated this subject and for a number of very fruitful discussions which followed. We furthermore thank A. Stocco for successfully undertaking the first endeavours into this very complex subject,¹⁴ leaving us with a much clearer idea for a strategy on how to penetrate

the unusual properties of catanionic foams. D.V. thanks the "Triangle de la Physique" (project SURFOAM) for a postdoctoral fellowship. We also thank the ESA Map program (project "Hydrodynamics of wet foams") for financial support. D.C. thanks Luc Belloni for helpful discussions on Poisson-Boltzmann models.

References

- 1 I. Cantat, S. Cohen-Addad, F. Elias, F. Graner, R. Hohler, O. Pitois, F. Rouyer and A. Saint-Jalmes, *Mousses Liquides*, Belin, Paris, 2010.
- 2 D. Weaire and S. Hutzler, *The Physics of Foams*, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1999.
- 3 D. Langevin, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2000, 88, 209-222.
- 4 T. N. Hunter, R. J. Pugh, G. V. Franks and G. J. Jameson, *Adv. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2008, 137, 57-81.
- 5 S. E. Friberg, C. S. Wahn, B. Greene and R. Vangilder, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1984, 101, 593-595.
- 6 S. Guignot, S. Faure, M. Vignes-Adler and O. Pitois, *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, 2010, 65, 2579-2585.
- 7 R. M. Guillermic, A. Salonen, J. Emile and A. Saint-Jalmes, *Soft Matter*, 2009, 5, 4975-4982.
- 8 F. Carn, A. Colin, O. Pitois, M. Vignes-Adler and R. Backov, *Langmuir*, 2009, 25, 7847-7856.
- 9 K. Koczol, L. A. Lobo and D. T. Wasan, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1992, 150, 492-506.
- 10 N. D. Denkov, *Langmuir*, 2004, 20, 9463-9505.
- 11 E. W. Kaler, K. L. Herrington, A. K. Murthy and J. A. N. Zasadzinski, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, 96, 6698-6707.
- 12 G. Kume, M. Gallotti and G. Nunes, *J. Surfactants Deterg.*, 2008, 11, 1-11.
- 13 J. Eastoe, J. Dalton, P. Rogueda, D. Sharpe, J. Dong and J. R. P. Webster, *Langmuir*, 1996, 12, 2706-2711.
- 14 A. Stocco, D. Carriere, M. Cottat and D. Langevin, *Langmuir*, 2010, 26, 10663-10669.
- 15 H. Lange and M. J. Schwuger, *Colloid Polym. Sci.*, 1971, 243, 120128.
- 16 T. Gilanyi, R. Meszaros and I. Varga, *Langmuir*, 2000, 16, 3200-3205.
- 17 T.-H. Chou, Y.-S. Lin, W.-T. Li and C.-H. Chang, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2008, 321, 384-392.
- 18 B. Sohrabi, H. Gharibi, B. Tajik, S. Javadian and M. Hashemianzadeh, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2008, 112, 14869-14876.
- 19 Y. Wang, C. M. Pereira, E. F. Marques, R. O. Brito, E. S. Ferreira and F. Silva, *Thin Solid Films*, 2006, 515, 2031-2037.
- 20 K. Golemanov, N. D. Denkov, S. Tcholakova, M. Vethamuthu and A. Lips, *Langmuir*, 2008, 24, 9956-9961.
- 21 E. H. Lucassen-Reynders, *Colloid Polym. Sci.*, 1972, 250, 356-359.
- 22 L. Chen, J.-X. Xiao, K. Ruan and J. Ma, *Langmuir*, 2002, 18, 72507252.

- 23 J. D. Coppock, K. Krishan, M. Dennin and B. G. Moore, *Langmuir*, 2009, 25, 5006-5011.
- 24 D. Blankschtein, A. Shiloach and N. Zoeller, *Curr. Opin. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1997, 2, 294-300.
- 25 A. Khan and E. F. Marques, *Curr. Opin. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1999, 4, 402-410.
- 26 R. G. Laughlin, *Colloids Surf., A*, 1997, 128, 27-38.
- 27 H. Li and J. Hao, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2008, 112, 10497-10508.
- 28 B. Novales, A. Riaublanc, L. Navailles, B. r. n. Houinsou Houssou, C. Gailard, F. Nallet and J.-P. Douliez, *Langmuir*, 2010, 26, 53295334.
- 29 Y. Michina, D. Carriere, C. Mariet, M. Moskura, P. Berthault, L. Belloni and T. Zemb, *Langmuir*, 2009, 25, 698-706.
- 30 Y. Michina, D. Carriere, T. Charpentier, R. Brito, E. F. Marques, J. P. Douliez and T. Zemb, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2010, 114, 1932-1938.
- 31 D. Kopetzki, Y. Michina, T. Gustavsson and D. Carriere, *Soft Matter*, 2009, 5, 4212-4218.
- 32 G. Bealle, J. Jestin and D. Carriere, *Soft Matter*, 2011, 7, 1084-1089.
- 33 N. Delorme, J. F. Bardeau, D. Carriere, M. Dubois, A. Gourbil, H. Mohwald, T. Zemb and A. Fery, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2007, 111, 2503-2505.
- 34 A. Saint-Jalmes, M. U. Vera and D. J. Durian, *Eur.Phys.J.B*, 1999, 12, 67-73.
- 35 C. Stubenrauch and R. von Klitzing, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter*, 2003, 15, R1197-R1232.
- 36 K. D. Wantke and H. Fruhner, in *Drops and Bubbles in Interfacial Research*, ed. D. Moebius and R. Miller, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1998, vol. 6.
- 37 J. Benjamins, A. Cagna and E. H. LucassenReynders, *Colloids Surf., A*, 1996, 114, 245-254.
- 38 P. Erni, P. Fischer, E. J. Windhab, V. Kusnezov, H. Stettin and J. Lauger, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, 2003, 74, 4916-4924.
- 39 S. G. Oh and J. C. Slattery, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1978, 67, 516525.
- 40 E. Maurer, L. Belloni, T. Zemb and D. Carriere, *Langmuir*, 2007, 23, 6554-6560.
- 41 D. Carriere, L. Belloni, B. Deme, M. Dubois, C. Vautrin, A. Meister and T. Zemb, *Soft Matter*, 2009, 5, 4983-4990.
- 42 P. Panniza, D. Roux, V. Vuillaume, C. Y. D. Lu and M. E. Cates, *Langmuir*, 1996, 12, 248-252.
- 43 N. D. Denkov, S. Tcholakova, K. Golemanov, K. P. Ananthapadmanabhan and A. Lips, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2008, 100, 138301.
- 44 H. M. Princen, *The Structure, Mechanics, and Rheology of Concentrated Emulsions and Fluid Foams*, Marcel Dekker, 2000.
- 45 D. Langevin, *Viscoelasticity of Monolayers*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., 2002.
- 46 D. Langevin, *ChemPhysChem*, 2008, 9, 510-522.
- 47 D. A. Edwards, H. Brenner and D. T. Wasan, *Interfacial Transport Processes and Rheology*, Butterworth-Heinemann, Stonheam, USA, 1991.
- 48 H. M. Wyss, K. Miyazaki, J. Mattsson, Z. Hu, D. R. Reichman and D. A. Weitz, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2007, 98, 238303-238304.
- 49 G. Espinosa and D. Langevin, *Langmuir*, 2009, 25, 12201-12207.

- 50 D. Y. Zang, D. Langevin, B. P. Binks and B. B. Wei, *Phys. Rev. E*, 2010, 81.
- 51 R. Krishnaswamy, S. Majumdar and A. K. Sood, *Langmuir*, 2007, 23, 12951-12958.
- 52 K. Miyazaki, H. M. Wyss, D. A. Weitz and D. R. Reichman, *Europhys. Lett.*, 2006, 75, 915-921.
- 53 B. Rullier, M. A. V. Axelos, D. Langevin and B. Novales, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2009, 336, 750-755.
- 54 S. Tcholakova, N. D. Denkov and A. Lips, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2008, 10, 1608-1627.
- 55 I. Cantat, S. Cohen-Addad, F. Elias, F. Graner, R. Hohler, O. Pitois, F. Rouyer and A. Saint-Jalmes, *Mousses Liquides*, Belin, Paris, 2010.
- 56 D. Weaire, S. Hutzler, G. Verbist and E. Peters, *Adv. Chem. Phys.*, 1997, 102, 315-374.
- 57 A. Salonen, D. Langevin, W. Drenckhan, E. Rio and A. Saint-Jalmes, *European Roads Review*, 2010, Fall.
- 58 D. Georgieva, A. Cagna and D. Langevin, *Soft Matter*, 2009, 5, 2063– 2071.
- 59 C. Sanchez, L. Rozes, F. Ribot, C. Laberty-Robert, D. Grosso, C. Sassoie, C. Boissiere and L. Nicole, *C. R. Chim.*, 2010, 13, 3-39.
- 60 A. Testouri, C. Honorez, A. Barillee, D. Langevin and W. Drenckhan, *Macromolecules*, 2010, 43, 6166-6173.
- 61 R. Backov, *Soft Matter*, 2006, 2, 452-464.
- 62 A. van der Net, A. Gryson, M. Ranft, F. Elias, C. Stubenrauch and W. Drenckhan, *Colloids Surf., A*, 2009, 346, 5-10.
- 63 N. Schelero, H. Lichtenfeld, H. Zastrow, H. Möhwald, M. Dubois and T. Zemb, *Colloids Surf., A*, 2009, 337, 146-153.

Fig. 1 (Left) Confocal microscopy images of the initially prepared 1wt% catanionic mixture, which was dialysed for 125 h and labelled with anionic Oregon green. The inset photograph represents the gel-like behavior of the catanionic mixture. (Centre and right) Diluted solutions show well individualised vesicles.

Fig. 2 (a) Bulk stress-strain curves of the catanionic suspension ($c = 0.5$ wt%) at angular frequencies of 1 and 10 rad/s. At low frequencies the system presents a non-linear viscoelastic behaviour, exhibiting a yield stress $\sigma_y \approx 0.5$ mPa ($\epsilon_y = 1.5\%$). In contrast, at high frequencies the system behaves fluid-like. (b) Variation of the storage and loss moduli with the angular frequency at a constant strain in the linear regime, $\epsilon = 1\%$ ($c = 0.5$ wt%). (c) Variation of the viscosity as a function of shear rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ (with $\dot{\epsilon} = \epsilon\omega$ at $\epsilon = 1\%$) for two different catanionic concentrations. While mixtures with a concentration of 0.5 wt% experience shear thinning, the ones with $c = 0.1$ wt% behave Newtonian.

Fig. 3 Image sequence of a cationic foam ($c = 0.5\text{wt}\%$) generated by hand-shaking. The foams do not coalesce, coarsen very slowly and maintain a significant amount of liquid in comparison to standard surfactant foams with the same structural properties.

Fig. 4 Evolution of the foam volume generated from a cationic mixture ($c = 0.5\text{wt}\%$) using turbulent mixing. A period of slow drainage is followed by a long-term stability.

Fig. 5 Comparison of foamability (middle column) and foam stability (right column) of a sonicated (bottom row) and non-sonicated (top row) cationic mixture ($c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$). Foams are produced by handshaking. Sonicated mixtures foam much less but make equally stable foams.

Fig. 6 (Top) Dynamic surface tension curves for cationic mixtures at various bulk concentrations ($c = 0.001, 0.01, 0.1\text{wt}\%$) measured using the rising bubble technique. (Bottom) As the surface tension drops the interfacial dilational elasticity E shoots to values which are too high to be measured with our technique (non-Laplacian bubble shapes).

Fig. 7 Comparison of the dynamic surface tension for sonicated and non-sonicated catanionic mixtures.

Fig. 8 Variation of the interfacial stress (a) and interfacial storage and loss moduli (b) as a function of the strain applied by the bicone to the interface when it oscillates at a constant angular frequency $\omega = 6.2 \text{ rad s}^{-1}$, for a bulk concentration of catanionic mixture of 0.1 wt% (bulk shear moduli, $G'' \approx 0.043 \text{ Pa}$; $G' \approx 0$).

Fig. 9 Oscillatory measurements of the interfacial storage and loss moduli for the adsorbed film created at the air/water interface by the diffusion of the catanionic mixture for the three different concentrations ($c = 0.001, 0.01, 0.1 \text{ wt}\%$). The inset shows the evolution of the characteristic time of the crossover between G'_i and G''_i as a function of the concentration of catanionic mixture.

Fig. 10 Progressive thinning of catanionic films in the Thin Film Pressure Balance (TFPB) for various concentrations: (a) $c = 0.01\text{wt}\%$ (b) $c = 0.05\text{wt}\%$ and (c) $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$ after 24 hour equilibrium time. The applied pressure difference is 2000 Pa (images from left to right every 10 min).

Fig. 11 Corrugated film thickness in a foam film made from cationic mixtures. This film was stable for several days.

Fig. 12 Confocal microscopy images of foams created from cationic mixture at bulk concentrations of $c = 0.1\text{wt}\%$ (top) and $c = 1\text{wt}\%$ (bottom). The larger ($> 50\mu \text{ m}$) dark circles are air bubbles, the smaller ($< 20\mu \text{ m}$) circles are vesicles.

Fig. 13 Generation (a) and stability (b) of cationic foams at two different concentrations ($c = 0.05$ and $0.5\text{wt}\%$). Foams are generated at a gas flow rate of 35 mL min^{-1} . (c) Images of foams at different times after generation for different concentrations.

Fig. 14 Variation of the average bubble size with gas flow rate in the FoamScan device.

Fig. 15 Foamability: foam height as a function of time during foam generation at three different gas flow rates for a CTABr solution (a) and a catanionic mixture ($c = 0.5\text{wt}\%$) (c). Foam stability (b) and (d): foam height as a function of foam age for the same systems.

Fig. 16 Liquid fraction at 6.5 cm foam height during foam generation (a and c) and as a function of foam age (b and d) for a CTABr solution (a and b) and a cationic mixture (c and d).